

mixed in 1:1 molecular proportions and heated for about 15 to 30 minutes on a water bath. In certain cases (vide expt. 8 to 11, Table I) the reaction was carried out in ethereal solution at room temperature; on evaporation of the ether and addition of a little ethanol, the condensate solidified to a crystalline powder which was crystallisable from ethanol in each case except in expt. 10 and 11 (Table I). M.p's., analyses, etc. of these are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

1,5-Disubstituted 2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets

S.No.	Reactants.	1,5-Disubst. 2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret formed.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Reqd.
1	S-Benzylphenyl-T + phenyl-I	1,5-Diphenyl.*	97-98°	..	..	..
2	S-Benzyl- <i>o</i> -tolyl-T + <i>o</i> -tolyl-I	1,5-Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	128°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ S ₂	10.23	10.37
3	S-Benzyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl-T + <i>p</i> -tolyl-I	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	126-27°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ S ₂	10.33	10.37
4	S-Benzyl- <i>p</i> -phenetyl-T + <i>p</i> -phenetyl-I	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -phenetyl-	101-102°	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	9.02	9.03
5	S-Benzyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl-T + phenyl-I	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-phenyl-	70-81°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂	10.53	10.74
6	S-Benzylphenyl-T + methyl-I	1-Phenyl-5-methyl-	104°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	13.18	13.33
7	S-Benzyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl-T + methyl-I	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-methyl-	116°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂	12.68	12.74
8	S-Benzylmethyl-T + phenyl-I	1-Methyl-5-phenyl-	133°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	12.98	13.33
9	S-Benzylmethyl-T + <i>p</i> -tolyl-I	1-Methyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	112°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂	12.72	12.74
10	S-Benzylmethyl-T + methyl-I	1,5-Dimethyl-	81°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	16.73	16.60
11	S-Benzylmethyl-T + Ethyl-I	1-Methyl-5-ethyl-	72-73°	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	15.42	15.73

*Johnson and Elmer, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1903, 30, 177, recorded m.p. 98-100°

T—denotes isothiocarbamide.

I—denotes isothiocyanate.

Debenzylation of 1,5-Disubstituted-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets: Formation of 1,5-Disubstituted-2,4-dithiobiurets.—The desired 1,5-disubstituted-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret was dissolved in ethanolic ammonia or 5 to 10% ethanolic solution of sodium sulphide and a stream of hydrogen sulphide passed for 1 to 3 hours. The solution was filtered and diluted

with water or acidified when the expected dithiobiuret precipitated which was collected and crystallised from ethanol (vide Table II).

TABLE II

1,5-Disubstituted 2,4-dithiobiurets (obtained by reduction of the related S-benzyliso derivatives)

S.No.	1,5-Disubst. 2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret reduced.	1,5-Disubst. 2,4-dithiobiuret formed.	M.P.	Formula	Found.	Reqd.
1	1,5-Diphenyl-	1,5-Diphenyl.*	141-45°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	N : 14.32%	14.63%
2	1,5-Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	1,5-Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	113-14°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	N : 13.01	13.33
3	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	142°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	C : 61.67 H : 5.45 N : 13.25	60.95 5.39 13.33
4	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -phenetyl-	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -phenetyl-	134°	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	N : 11.25	11.20
5	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-phenyl-	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-phenyl- (or 1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-)	124°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	N : 13.64	13.95
6	1-Phenyl-5-methyl-	1-Phenyl-5-methyl- (or 1-methyl-5-phenyl-)	135°	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	C : 47.88 H : 4.76 N : 18.36	48.00 4.88 18.66
7	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-methyl-	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-methyl- (or 1-methyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-)	164°	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	C : 50.20 H : 5.50 N : 17.55	50.20 5.43 17.57
8	1-Methyl-5-phenyl-	1-Methyl-5-phenyl- (or 1-phenyl-5-methyl-)	This was found identical with the product described under 6 above.			
9	1-Methyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	1-Methyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl- (or 1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-methyl-)	This was found identical with the product described under 7 above.			
10	1,5-Dimethyl-	1,5-Dimethyl-	148°	C ₄ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	C : 30.12 H : 5.88 N : 26.02	29.44 5.52 25.76

*Underwood and Dains, *Kansas Univ. Sci. Bull.*, 1936, 24, 5; *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 3399, recorded m.p. 149°.

Oxidation of 1,5-Disubstituted-2,4-dithiobiurets: Formation of the Related Dithiazolidines.—The dithiobiuret was dissolved in ethanol and a slight excess of bromine in the same solvent was added with stirring. The related dithiazolidine hydrobromides separated immediately or on keeping. These on treatment with ammonia or alkali afforded the free dithiazolidine bases which were stable to alkali. The dithiazolidine hydrobromides and their free bases were crystallised from ethanol; their m. p.'s and analyses are presented in Table III. It is interesting to note that 3,5-disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithi-

azolidines are stable to hot alkaline solutions unlike the 3,5-disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines which decompose into cyanothiocarbamides and sulphur.

TABLE III

3,5-Disubstituted imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines.

S.No.	1,5-Disubst. 2,4-dithiobiuret oxidised.	3,5-Disubst.imino- 1,2,4-dithiazolidine.	M.P.	Free base Formula	Free base	
					Found	Reqd.
1	1,5-Diphenyl-	3,5-Diphenylimino- hydrobromide, m.p. 108°; eq.wt. found 362; reqd. 366.	179-80°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	N : 14.38%	14.72%
2	1,5-Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	3,5-Di- <i>o</i> -tolylimino- hydrobromide, m.p. 248°; eq.wt. found 397; reqd. 394	166°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	N : 13.21	13.41
3	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	3,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolylimino- hydrobromide, m.p. 218°; eq.wt. found 397; reqd. 304	188°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	C : 61.01 H : 4.55 N : 13.24	61.34 4.78 13.41
4	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -phenetyl-	3,5-Di- <i>p</i> -phenetyl- imino-hydrobromide, m.p. 218°	186°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂	N : 11.04	11.28
5	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-phenyl-	5- <i>p</i> -Tolylimino-3-phenylimino- hydrobromide, m.p. 228°	196°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	N : 14.64	14.79
6	1-Phenyl-5-methyl-	5-Phenylimino-3-methylimino- hydrobromide, m.p. 198°; eq. wt. found 301; reqd. 304	136°	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	C : 47.47 H : 4.03 N : 18.68	46.43 4.03 18.83
7	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-methyl-	5- <i>p</i> -Tolylimino-3-methylimino- hydrobromide, m.p. 231°; eq.wt. found 314; reqd. 316	158°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	C : 50.75 H : 4.13 N : 17.43	50.83 4.64 17.72
8	1,5-Dimethyl-	3,5-Dimethylimino- hydrobromide, m.p. 281°	168°	C ₄ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	N : 25.86	26.08

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